

The systematical analysis about the effect of Knowledge spillover on technological innovation capability

Authors : Tian Tian, Tian Baoguang

Abstract : The paper studies implications between knowledge spillovers and technological innovation capability in the following three aspects: firstly, the paper debates on the effect of knowledge spillover on some perspectives of technological innovation ability; secondly, it discusses how different roles of knowledge spillover affect the technological innovation capability; finally, the paper creates the model of the factors of knowledge spillovers influencing to technological innovation capability. It concludes that knowledge spillovers affect all the main aspects of technological innovation ultimately to impact of technological innovation capabilities.

Keywords : Knowledge Spillover; Technological Innovation Capability; Innovation Cluster; Innovation Network Factors

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